

Workers, Inhabitants, and Environments of the Global South Pay the Price of the Energy Transition ¹

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In the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) — a Central African country that was a Belgian colony until the 1960s and today accounts for approximately 74% of global cobalt production — workers transport raw ore on bicycles, exposing themselves to toxic metals and facing heightened risks of severe illnesses.

Image: Roy Maconachie (2024).

In late June, the Energy Institute (EI) released the [Statistical Review of World Energy 2025](#) ¹, reporting that all major global energy sources reached record levels in 2024, reflecting the [steady growth in global demand](#) ². Currently, [around 80% of the world's energy consumption](#) ³ still comes from fossil fuels, exacerbating [pollution and accelerating climate change](#) ⁴. The energy transition has progressed, driven primarily by [falling costs of solar and wind power](#) ⁵, which together accounted for [86.5% of renewable energy](#) ⁶ investments between 2013 and 2022.

Despite their essential role, [these technologies rely heavily on mineral inputs](#) ⁷, due to their [lower energy density](#) ⁸ and the [shorter operational lifespan of equipment](#) ⁹. A wind turbine can require up to [nine times more minerals](#) ¹⁰ than a gas-fired power plant of equivalent capacity,

while electric vehicles demand **substantial quantities of materials**¹⁰ for their large batteries. Given the **limited scale of recycling**¹¹, **pressure for new mineral extraction continues to grow**⁷. Projections indicate that, by 2050, mineral demand could **rise by more than 200% in the electricity sector and by 350% in transportation**¹².

Mining, however, generates **billions of tons of waste annually and consumes vast amounts of water and energy**¹⁴, underscoring that “green” technologies also carry **significant environmental costs**⁷. Moreover, a considerable share of so-called **critical minerals**¹⁵ — those essential to low-carbon technologies — is sourced from countries in the Global South, encompassing **nations in Africa, Latin America, and Asia**¹⁶ that are generally characterized by lower income levels, greater inequality, and a history of colonization.

Position	Cobalt (2023)		Nickel (2022)		Copper (2022)			
	Country	%	Country	%	Country	%		
1st	DR Congo	73.9 %	Indonesia	48.6 %	Chile	24 %		
2nd	Indonesia	7.4 %	Philippines	10.0 %	Peru	10 %		
3rd	Russia	3.8 %	Russia	6.7 %	DR Congo	10 %		
4th	Australia	2.0 %	New Caledonia	5.8 %	China	9 %		
5th	Madagascar	1.7 %	Australia	4.9 %	USA	6 %		
6th	Philippines	1.7 %	Canada	4.3 %	Russia	5 %		
7th	Cuba	1.4 %	China	3.3 %	Indonesia	4 %		
8th	New Caledonia	1.3 %	Brazil	2.5 %	Australia	4 %		
9th	P. New Guinea	1.3 %			Zambia	4 %		
10th					Mexico	3 %		
Other (Sum)		5.5 %	Other (Sum)		13.9 %	Other (Sum)		21 %

Position	Lithium (2023)		Rare Earths (2023)		
	Country	%	Country	%	
1st	Australia	46.6 %	China	68.3 %	
2nd	Chile	23.8 %	USA	12.3 %	
3rd	China	17.9 %	Myanmar	10.6 %	
4th	Argentina	5.2 %	Australia	5.1 %	
5th	Brazil	2.7 %	Thailand	2.0 %	
6th	Zimbabwe	1.8 %	India	0.8 %	
Other (Sum)		2.0 %	Other (Sum)		0.9 %

Countries of the global South

Table: Global South countries, highlighted, lead global extraction of critical minerals for the energy transition. Source: Authors - (Stacciarini; Gonçalves, 2025).

In these regions, mineral exploitation often **serves the interests of multinational corporations**¹⁷, which benefit from lenient regulations, governments economically reliant on mining, and weakened civil societies — conditions that reduce operational costs and maximize profits. As a result, local communities bear the brunt of socio-environmental harm, while the benefits of the energy transition are largely concentrated in the countries of the Global North.

Cobalt

Cobalt is a critical component in battery manufacturing, particularly for electric vehicles, which accounted for approximately **40% of global demand in 2023**¹⁸. This demand is projected to **double by 2030**¹⁹. Around 74% of global cobalt production is concentrated in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) (see Table) — a Central African nation that was a Belgian colony until the 1960s — where extraction often occurs **without adequate safety measures**²⁰, exposing workers to toxic metals and significantly increasing the risk of severe illnesses.

In addition to operations run by large-scale mining companies, thousands of Congolese engage in artisanal mining under highly precarious conditions. Recent investigations have documented the use of **child labor, fatalities resulting from mine collapses, and the unsafe handling of ore**²¹ by women and children.

Women wash raw cobalt ore after extraction, exposing themselves to severe risks of poisoning.

Image: Roy Maconachie (2024).

The cobalt extracted **is sold to intermediaries**²¹ and subsequently enters global supply chains, ultimately reaching major corporations that thus avoid direct association with human rights violations. Reports by organizations such as RAID and Afrewatch have also documented **water contamination in areas surrounding the mines**²², with adverse effects on fishing, agriculture, and community health. These impacts include increased incidence of gynecological, dermatological, and reproductive disorders.

Nickel

Nickel is a key material for the production of batteries and energy storage systems, with **demand expected to grow exponentially**¹⁰ in the coming decades. Indonesia — a former Dutch colony that gained independence in 1945 — currently leads global production, supplying roughly half of the world's nickel (see Table) after **increasing its output sixfold**²³ between 2010 and 2023.

Despite its strategic importance to the energy transition, a substantial share of Indonesia's nickel is **extracted and processed using coal**²⁴, one of the most **polluting energy sources**²⁵. Coal consumption in the country has **risen sharply in recent years**²⁶, making Indonesia the **world's third-largest producer, eighth-largest consumer, and seventh-largest emitter of CO₂**²⁷.

Nickel mining and smelting have led to significant **contamination of soils, water bodies, and coastal zones across the Indonesian archipelago**²⁸, with severe impacts on ecosystems and on

communities reliant on fishing and agriculture. Working conditions in the sector are also precarious, with at least **dozens of fatalities** ²⁹ reported in nickel mines between 2015 and 2022.

Nickel mines expand across Indonesia, destroying forests and polluting the environment.

Image: Garry Lotulung (2024).

Copper

Copper, the non-precious metal with the highest electrical conductivity, is **indispensable for wind turbines, solar panels, electric vehicles, and modern power grids** ³⁰. Its growing relevance to the energy transition has **driven global production from 16 million metric tons in 2010 to 22 million in 2023** ³¹, with forecasts indicating continued growth in the coming decades. Chile leads global production (24%), followed by Peru and the Democratic Republic of Congo (10% each) (see Table), although the sector is largely **controlled by multinational corporations headquartered in the Global North** ³².

In Chile, the socio-environmental impacts of copper mining are considerable. In the country's north, **Indigenous communities are exposed to toxic dust** ³³, increasing the risk of disease. On the central coast, the Ventanas Smelter was **shut down in 2023** ³⁴ following sustained protests against **decades of pollution** ³⁵ that had turned the region into a “**sacrifice zone**,”³⁶ marked by

recurrent outbreaks of illnesses linked to air, water, and soil contamination.

Fishermen collect pollutant residues on a beach near the Ventanas copper smelter in Quintero Bay, Chile.

Image: Michelle Carrere (2019).

In Peru, investigations have documented [water contamination and elevated levels of toxic metals](#)³⁷ — such as arsenic, lead, and mercury — among residents in [areas affected by mining projects](#)³⁸. In the Democratic Republic of Congo, challenges mirror those observed in cobalt extraction, including [precarious labor conditions, environmental degradation, and human rights violations](#)³⁹.

Lithium

Global lithium consumption rose by [686% between 2010 and 2023](#)⁴⁰, driven primarily by lithium-ion batteries for electric vehicles, which accounted for [87% of demand in 2023](#)⁴⁰. While Australia leads global production (46.6%), approximately [60% of known reserves are located in Latin America](#)⁴¹, particularly within the so-called “Lithium Triangle” — formed by Chile, Argentina, and Bolivia — which already supplies about 30% of global output (see Table).

Extraction occurs in salt deserts through the [pumping of brine to the surface, followed by evaporation in large open-air ponds](#)⁴². This [highly water-intensive process](#)⁴³ has reduced water availability in arid regions, [undermining agriculture, livestock farming, and the livelihoods of local communities](#)⁴⁴. Beyond soil and ecosystem contamination, concerns include the [limited number of jobs created, modest royalty revenues, and the escalation of socio-environmental conflicts](#)⁴³.

Lithium mining in northern Argentina has caused pollution and river depletion, triggering multiple socio-environmental impacts for local communities.

Image: Maria Paula Gaido (2024).

Rare Earth Elements

Rare earth elements (REEs) — [a group of 17 strategic metals](#)⁴⁵ used in the [production of magnets, batteries, metal alloys, and advanced technological devices](#)⁴⁶ — are essential to the energy transition. [Global production rose from 133,000 metric tons in 2010 to 350,000 metric tons in 2023](#)⁴⁷, underscoring their growing importance in low-carbon technologies.

China, the world’s leading producer (68.3%) (see Table), experiences significant environmental impacts from rare earth extraction, including [water and soil contamination caused by the intensive use of chemicals in mining and processing](#)⁴⁸. These practices pose serious [health risks to nearby populations](#)⁴⁹.

Myanmar — a former British colony and the world's third-largest producer (see Table) — doubled its output between 2018 and 2023⁵⁰. However, this expansion has been marked by severe irregularities, including illegal mining, control by armed militias, absence of environmental regulation, and serious human rights violations⁵¹. Reports document widespread illness, fatalities from accidents and chemical exposure⁵², and rising levels of violence, drug trafficking, and prostitution⁵¹ in mining areas.

Rare earth extraction in Myanmar causes severe socio-environmental impacts. After resource depletion, many mines are abandoned without any environmental remediation.

Image: Global Witness (2022).

Envisioning a Possible Future?

Given the challenges outlined above, it is imperative to reconsider the trajectory of the energy transition to ensure it does not replicate — or exacerbate — historical patterns of exploitation in the Global South⁷. Achieving a truly just transition requires that these territories be recognized not merely as suppliers of resources under fragile legal frameworks, but as central actors in shaping a new model of development. This, in turn, demands confronting the structural asymmetries that define global productive and geoeconomic dynamics.

As a contribution to this debate, we underscore the urgency of: (1) strengthening traceability mechanisms for critical minerals; (2) establishing stricter regulatory frameworks, with effective environmental oversight and corporate accountability; (3) ensuring the active participation of local communities in decision-making processes; (4) fostering local value chains through value-added production in the mineral sector; (5) converting compensations and royalties into investments in social infrastructure and strategies for economic diversification; (6) promoting technological innovation aimed at the recycling and reuse of critical minerals; (7) rethinking global production and consumption patterns in light of the planet's ecological limits. Only through such measures will it be possible to advance an energy transition that genuinely promotes socio-environmental justice on a global scale.

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